

Development and Implementation of a Hand Gesture Recognition System Using OpenCV

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ABSTRACT - With the development of sophisticated devices, the system may now be virtually operated with the help of human gestures. One of the most intriguing and difficult research areas in the world of image processing and pattern recognition in recent years has been Writing in Air. Hand gesture detection systems have received a lot of interest recently due to their wide range of applications and capability for efficient human-computer interaction. The usage of gestures can reduce the usage of most of the hardware components such as the keyboard, mouse, and stylus. In this paper we implemented real-time hand detection using Mediapipe, finger detection and gesture recognition using OpenCV, Manipulation of brushes and shapes is implemented by recognizing the hand gesture. The hand gesture letters are standardized using text recognition algorithms. This system can be very effective for interactive and fun-based learning for toddlers, for people with hearing disabilities.

Keywords- Air writing, Hand Gesture recognition, OCR tesseract,pygame

I. INTRODUCTION

Freehand digital drawing software called Air Canvas records hand gestures and displays them on a PiTFT display. In the process of recognition, Air Canvas makes use of a Raspberry Pi, the Pi Camera, and OpenCV. We had an interest in digital painting and intelligent photo recognition software, which gave rise to the concept for Air Canvas. The OpenCV package, with its simple-to-use processing capabilities for real-time computer vision, is one of the Assembly's favourite toolkits. Air Canvas, which was initially created as a way of communication for the deaf, is now extensively used for emailing, taking brief notes, and enhancing design. In spite of their widespread use in virtual reality, articulated hand-tracking systems are rarely used in consumer applications because of their high price and complexity. With the exception of its accuracy in gesture and movement, it is simple to use and apply. This programme can only be used by smart and intelligent devices and essentially requires technical knowledge.

Although the use of IOT devices has been considered, it has not yet been put into practice. A handwriting recognizer works faster when writing word-by-word than a character recognizer does. The open-source library has been very helpful for processing live video capture on the fly with minimum overhead, producing excellent results with little code. It works well with Python. By including the start and stop elements that provide consumers a clear notion about processes that are in line, the already existent air canvas may be improved. Brushes that support design creation and improve the application's aesthetic appeal can be added. Python was used to create the programme, which was then tested in a variety of settings with variable lighting. This software-based solution is simple, quick, and easy to use in the relevant sense. Although regional languages can be added, Air Canvas currently only supports

English as a global language in its workflow. A speaker who reads aloud from captured content can be a highlight to improve comprehension.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

In [1], this paper developed a concept of presenting an idea in real-world space. It utilizes OpenCV to recognize the user's finger point. Brilliant lines can be drawn in any place the client wants. No compelling reason to contact the PC once the program is run. The user is unable to modify the colour or thickness of the line.

In [2], aim of this paper is to enable users to draw characters in real-time by utilizing a predetermined object to track movement, which is fed into the system. By reducing the reliance on paper, this project seeks to make drawing or writing in real-time easier. Furthermore, it eliminates the need for a mouse or input pen. It is worth noting that the process cannot be paused or stopped midway.

In [3], this paper, "air writing" involves using hand or finger user is unable to modify the colour or thickness of the line movements to write linguistic characters or words in the air, which are then recognized by the system using six-degree-of-freedom hand motion data. The project includes two levels of air-writing, namely motion characters and motion words. A hidden Markov Model is utilized to model and recognize air-writing. Based on the findings, air-writing can be considered appropriate for short and occasional text input on a user interface that relies on the motion. However, the text produced through this method is not displayed in a consistent format.

In [4], the objective of this paper is to interpret gestures automatically by utilizing computer vision. This project presents a vision-based method for identifying hand gestures that utilize transfer learning and can control computers through six static and eight dynamic hand movements. The technique involves three essential stages: detecting the hand's shape, monitoring its movement if it is in motion, and converting the gathered data into the appropriate command. Since it relies on visual information, this approach may not be suitable for individuals without vision.

In [5], This model suggests probabilistic methods for visual tracking of a three-dimensional geometric hand model utilizing monocular image sequences. We utilized the naturally occurring graphical structure of the geometric models typically used for hand-tracking to create a potent hand-tracking method using the nonparametric belief propagation (NBP) algorithm. Using the graphical structure, NBP greatly decreases the complexity of these distributions, enhancing their robustness. For identifying 3D objects, the currently employed algorithms are challenging to understand and ineffectively track precise hand gestures. The normal text does not recognise air writing.

In [6], one of the rapidly developing areas of research in the field of gesture recognition, the conversion of finger movements to text, has a relatively straightforward and cost-effective answer in this system. This system is designed in such a way that it can recognize the English alphabet drawn in the air and translate it into text with just a basic Webcam. Using MATLAB Software, which provides straightforward, understandable, and effective code structures, this system is implemented. Any computer that has a Web Camera and the necessary setups can have the system installed. This system is unquestionably a baseline for the more recent breakthrough of translating finger movement to text and being able to see. This is a simple version of air canvas, does not provide more features and no additional

benefits of brush manipulations and colour palette.

In [7], this technique employs video to detect finger spellings in real-time. The automatic translation of sign language remains to be the most challenging and challenging task for video recognition and processing. This paper expressly recommends employing a piecewise linear activation function on two neural networks for colour classification and hand position identification in order to perform video processing in real-time. A simple neural network is used to recognise Brazilian sign language from video. does not provide easy-to-use brush manipulations that would let the user modify the size of the brush.

In [8], this model uses Jordan's recurrent neural network-based dynamic hand gesture recognition system (JRNN). A set of approved movements are modelled using a number of common static images, or postures. The proposed system arranges the input postures that are present in the input video frames first, and the JRNN locates the input gesture by identifying the temporal behaviour of the posture sequence. To enhance the JRNN's ability to recognise the temporal behaviour of its input sequence, a novel training technique has been created. The planned gesture recognition system has been put to the test to see if it works, and the results are given. uses JRNN to recognise gestures in real-time but is deficient in brush capabilities and other aspects for textrecognition in the air.

In [9], the four factors in this project are choosing an acceptable object representation, choosing features for tracking, identifying objects, and tracking them. Object tracking algorithms are crucial for a number of real-world applications, including autonomous surveillance, video indexing, and vehicle navigation. Only smart and intelligent devices can use this application and basically requires technical knowledge. The use of IOT devices has been given thought but has not been brought into implementation yet. Word-by-word writing is faster when a handwriting recognizer is used rather than a character recognizer. Rather than using the number of fingertips to control the real-time system, hand gestures with a pause can be employed. Occasionally our system notices fingertips in the distance and modifies their condition.

In [10], although articulated hand-tracking systems are frequently employed in virtual reality, due to their high cost and complexity, they are rarely used in consumer applications. In this study, we provide a low-cost, user-friendly technology that enables 3-D hand-articulated user input. Our method tracks a hand while it is donning a regular fabric glove with a unique pattern put on it. The pattern is made to make the posture estimation problem simpler, enabling us to track hands at interactive rates using a nearest-neighbour method. We outline several proofs-of-concept uses for the system that we think will lay the groundwork for novel modelling, animation control, and augmented reality interactions. To make choosing tasks easier, we can develop tools like a clicker or trigger. To facilitate immediate deployment in a larger range of scenarios, we can improve our camera calibration procedure. We outline several proofs-of-concept uses for the system that we think will lay the groundwork for novel modelling, animation control, and augmented reality interactions. To make choosing tasks easier, we can develop tools like a clicker or trigger. To facilitate immediate deployment in a larger range of scenarios, we can improve our camera calibration procedure.

In [11], with the development of technology, every industry must be modernized. With the development of sophisticated devices, the system may now be virtually operated with the help of human gestures. Sometimes while using paint, we find it difficult to sketch and wish we could just wave our hand and create anything from our thoughts. The development of a motion-to-text converter is one of Project Air

Canvas's areas of expertise. The current initiative uses technology or methodology that requires a lengthy procedure and a lot of time and allows us to draw simply by waving our hands. We developed this initiative, which makes use of cutting-edge technologies and simple techniques, to avoid or lessen these constraints. This makes the project more effective than the current one by using simple techniques or libraries like Mediapipe. We have used Mediapipe to construct an air canvas system in this system, which is an effective approach to tracking hand positions. We can streamline the image processing required to identify the positions of fingers with the aid of Mediapipe.

In [12], our thoughts can be communicated through writing, an integrated method of communication. Today, writing and typing are the two most common ways to capture information. In a loose manner, letters or words are scribbled with a marker or a finger. These wearable gadgets are able to observe and comprehend human behaviour. Gesture recognition is a computational method that uses mathematical algorithms to try to recognize and interpret human gestures. The software will use computer vision to track finger movement. Sending emails and SMS is another purpose for written text, among others. For those who are deaf with the help of this programme, people will be able to interact with the digital world more effectively while wearing smart apparel. The material can come alive by illustrating the unpopular reality of taxpayers. Works helpful for the impaired and Senior Citizens use this at their complex time.

In [13], this method develops probabilistic methods from monocular picture sequences, which are employed for geometric models, enabling visual tracking of a three-dimensional geometric hand model. Given that hand-tracking algorithms by nature have a graphic design, non-parametric belief propagation (NBP) algorithms were used to take advantage of this characteristic and create efficient hand-tracking algorithms. NBP significantly reduces these distributions' dimensionality using the graphical structure, which increases their robustness.

In [14], users can quickly create lines and circles in the interface with the light pen, and they can save the combination for use in subsequent drawings. Before the development of the touch screen and even the computer mouse, (GUI) was a novel means of interaction. Although the Sketchpad itself was never made accessible to the public, Sutherland's article on the Sketchpad's concepts is still frequently applied to the design of the sketching user interface for HTML, JavaScript, and Flask-based web application for improved versions of artistic scenarios from a deeper semantic level. Transferring hand-drawn sketches from one picture to another to process natural language.

In [15], one of the main objectives of digital art has been the creation of a hand gesture recognition system that can be used for digital handwriting. A keyboard, tablet, or another input device can be used to produce digital art like E-glove, digital pen, or stylus. On the other hand, hand motions are recognised using Python programming and machine learning techniques, enabling you to fluidly create naturally as technology develops. Systems for human-computer interaction (HCI) are becoming more and more necessary. Based on the video, the method for creating the text that uses a laptop camera and a hover mechanism is as follows. Moreover, they provide a natural user interface that eliminates the need for a keyboard, pen, or glove for character entry.

In [16], the method for writing English text in the air using a mobile camera is presented in this paper as a video-based pointing technique. English characters in printed images are recognised to identify handwriting. Additionally, the suggested method offers natural human system interaction in a way that

eliminates the need for a keyboard, pen, or gloves for text input. To recreate them at your fingertips, all you need is a mobile camera and a red marker. To recognise written characters, colour the video frame's fingertips red and then apply English character recognition to the image of the written character. The suggested approach additionally offers natural human system interaction that does not require a keyboard, pen, or gloves for text input.

III. METHODOLOGY

With the aid of motion tracking techniques (Mediapipe, OpenCV), people can use a technology called Air Canvas to write and draw in the air while simply waving their hands in front of the camera. By recording video of the action being performed, the web camera records the hand motion [6]. In this model, lines are drawn on a computer or canvas using hand motions. Here are a few techniques for implementing air canvas with Python's NumPy, OpenCV, Pandas, and Mediapipe modules.

1. Hand detection using Mediapipe: Mediapipe provides a hand-tracking solution that can be used to detect and track the movements of a user's hand. This can be used to determine the position of the hand and its movements.
2. Finger detection: Once the hand is detected, you can use OpenCV to segment the hand and detect the fingers. You can use techniques like contour detection, thresh holding, and morphological operations to identify the fingers.
3. Gesture recognition: You can use the position of the fingers to recognize gestures. For example, a closed fist can be used to select the brush, while an open hand can be used to erase.
4. Drawing on the canvas: Once a gesture is recognized, you can use OpenCV to draw on the screen or canvas. You can use functions like `cv2.line()` or `cv2.circle()` to draw shapes and lines.
5. Text Recognition: recognize the handwritten text from the user's hand movements and convert them into digital text that can be displayed on the canvas. It can use techniques such as Optical Character Recognition (OCR) and machine learning techniques.
6. Clearing the canvas: You can use a gesture to clear the canvas. For example, you can recognize a thumbs-up gesture to clear the canvas.

Fig 1 Workflow for Hand Gesture Recognition

IV. ALGORITHM

The proposed model uses a combination of computer vision, motion tracking, and machine learning techniques.

1. Capture video frames from the webcam.
2. Apply hand detection using the Mediapipe Hands model to detect the user's hand landmarks in the current frame.
 - i) If hand landmarks are not detected, go back to step 1
3. Map the detected hand landmarks to the 2D canvas plane.
4. Use the mapped 2D coordinates to update the state of the air canvas by drawing on the canvas using a specified color and brush size.
5. Check for user input such as changing the brush color or size, clearing the canvas, and shapes, clicking on exit, and updating the canvas state accordingly.
 - a. If the user closes the application or clicks the "Exit" button, exit the program.
 - b. else do: Update canvas after each user input.
6. Recognize the handwritten text by the user and convert it into Text.
7. Display the updated canvas on the screen.

Fig 2. Flowchart for Hand Gesture Recognition

V. RESULT

Fig 3. Hand Detection

Description: Applying hand detection using the Mediapipe, Hands model to detect the user's hand landmarks in the current frame.

Fig 4. Finger Detection

Description: After the hand is detected, then the OpenCV module segments the hand and detects the finger. Users can now write in air, which will be reflected on the output canvas

Fig 5. Clearing the Canvas

Description: Hand gestures can be used to clear the canvas or simply by moving a finger over a clear option.

VI. REFERENCES

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